

Effect of Ni Doping on the Thermoelectric Properties of $\text{YbCo}_2\text{Zn}_{20}$

Supporting Information

Figure S1. X-ray diffraction peaks taken through powder XRD for $\text{YbCo}_{2-x}\text{Ni}_x\text{Zn}_{20}$.